

Polyurethane Recycling towards a Smart Circular Economy

PUReSmart

Chance to Change

PU from collection to recycling

Polyurethanes (PU) are part of the six most important plastic materials worldwide for their use and economic value. Each year, more than 30 million mattresses are discarded in the European Union and around 90% of those mattresses are estimated to contain flexible PU foam (Europur 2021)

PUReSmart's ambition is thus to reshape the value chain of PU into a closed loop and transform PU from a long-lasting waste stream into a long-lasting raw material, since the transformation is a natural process and the chemistry works according to laws of nature.

This document briefly presents PUReSmart project and the main results of the sustainability evaluation, which aimed to identify potential environmental and social benefits from the innovative PU chemical recycling technology developed in the project.

*This document, corresponding to the Deliverable 6.8 "White paper issued to policy makers", has been written by Laura Zanchi, Simone Maranghi and Alessandra Zamagni, from Ecoinnovazione srl, within the framework of the PUReSmart Project (GA 814543).
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To do it better

Pills of PU flexible foam applications and waste management

Thermoset polyurethane (PU) products such as flexible and rigid foams are long-lasting, durable and useful in many different applications (e.g., furniture and bedding, thermal insulation, appliances, automotive & transportation). They are among the **six most important plastic materials produced worldwide** and promote comfort and safety in daily life. Compared with thermoplastic materials, recycling thermoset PU is a much more challenging process. **Nearly 90% of mattresses produced in the EU contain PU foam and almost all of furniture upholstery is made of PU foam.** According to the project, in this document, only flexible polyurethane foam is considered.

Recycling of polyurethane foams is primarily done on pre-consumer waste by a mechanical recycling process. Foams are chopped in small pieces and compressed with

European policy and legal framework

In the last decade, industry has come under pressure to address the impact of PU and other plastics' vast and problematic waste streams.

- The **European Green Deal** constitutes the EU's guiding policy framework for the transition to a more sustainable economy, aiming to make the continent climate neutral by 2050 (EC, 2019). **The foreseen reductions of 55% by 2030 and net-zero by 2050** will have repercussions for different choices to be made with regards to chemical recycling. Current developments will have to meet ambitious targets in terms of energy use reduction, at least leveling with emissions for the production of virgin material (Van Gaubergen and Block, 2022).
- **The Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP)** (EC, 2020) and the goal of transitioning to a 'circular economy' are an important part of the Green Deal. An important legislative

a binder in the rebond process. These recycled products are applied in carpet underlays, shock absorbing mats and acoustic products. The outlet markets are relatively limited and saturated.

Each year, around 40 million mattresses are discarded in the European Union, corresponding to 250-300 kt, while post-consumer furniture is estimated around 400 kt per year (Europur, 2021b). Currently, mattresses are known as the "bulky" waste stream, and it is difficult to obtain reliable public statistics on how they are treated. A recent estimation indicated that **49% of mattresses are landfilled in the European Union today**, 33% are sent to energy plants and 17% are recycled. While little data is available for furniture, the European Commission estimates that less than 10% of furniture is recycled across the EU (Europur, 2021a).

effort within the CEAP is the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR), which encompasses a thorough revision and expansion of the Ecodesign Directive and aims to develop a coherent legislative framework including a legally binding set of sustainability principles and long-term targets for the EU Member States' product policies, as well as implementation plans (EC, 2022). Within the framework product-specific legislation will be developed and furniture and mattresses are identified as priority product categories to target, among others (Van Gaubergen and Block, 2022).

- The **Waste Framework Directive (WFD)** has set ambitious objectives regarding the preparation for reuse and recycling targets: 55% to be achieved by 2025, 60% by 2030 and 65% by 2035. This target set certain nation states in motion to adopt 'extended producer responsi-

Each year, more than 30 million mattresses are discarded in the European Union, and about 90% of those mattresses are estimated to contain flexible PU foam. Flexible PU foam is the most popular filling material for upholstered furniture as more than 90% of these products contain a certain amount of **PU foam**¹. In the last decade, industry has come under pressure to address the impact of PU and other plastics' vast and problematic waste streams. Setting the direction for change, Europe's vision for a circular economy is starting to shift industrial goals and developments.

1 Europur (2021a, January 11). The Netherlands: a world-leader in mattress recycling [Press release]. <https://europur.org/the-netherlands-a-world-leader-in-mattress-recycling/>

bility' (EPR) schemes for mattresses. The ambitious targets of the WFD and the explicit reference to mattresses provide a direct push towards increasing and facilitating mattress recycling practices. As the market for mechan-

ical recycling seems to be reaching saturation and alternatives to chemical recycling seem scarce, chemical recycling can play an important role in the near future (Van Gaubergen and Block, 2022).

PUReSmart project Objectives

The PUReSmart project² (H2020 program, GA 814543) aimed at developing smart sorting technologies to separate a diverse range of PU materials into dedicated feedstocks that will be broken down into their basic components as inputs for existing PU products. PUReSmart targeted the recovery of over 90% of end-of-life PU with the goal of converting it into valuable inputs for new and known products to allow the transition from the current linear lifecycle of polyurethane products to a circular economy model.

The technology validation also involved the evaluation of its sustainability performance in comparison with the state-of-the-art. To do so, a life cycle-based sustainability assessment was carried out by considering environmental, social, and economic dimensions.

Results

The project consortium worked on the development of:

- a **chemolysis technology** that allows revalorisation of PU's building blocks
- **innovative sorting technologies** to separate a diverse range of PU materials into dedicated feedstocks which will be broken down into their basic components as inputs for existing PU products and as raw materials for the newly designed polymer.

The potential advantages and circularity of the PUReSmart technology were evaluated from the environmental and social point of view, by means of life cycle-based methods. **Environmental impacts were quantified according to the Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) methodology**, considering future scenarios where the new technology will be implemented, and according to two perspectives, which represent the two functions of the PUReSmart technology: waste management and secondary raw materials exploitation. **The social analysis was carried out building upon the Social Life Cycle Assessment methodology**, and primarily aimed at identifying and mapping the most relevant social aspects related to the introduction of innovative chemical recycling technologies for PU EoL mattresses. Moreover, social risks and effects were evaluated according to reference sectors conditions and experts' knowledge, considering the whole PU value chain.

2 <https://www.puresmart.eu/>

PUReSmart.

Sustainability assessment of the innovative PU chemical recycling technology

Principles of sustainability assessment

- A life cycle-based approach was applied, building upon the PEF methodology and the Social Life Cycle Assessment, as far the environmental and social analyses are concerned, and considering the perspectives of the PU value chain actors. The economic assessment was built upon the definition of the most likely business case scenarios for the exploitation of the PUReSmart technology.
- The views of the stakeholders of the PU value chain were included in the assessment for supporting the definition of “what matters” from the social point of view, when a technology like PUReSmart will be implemented into the market.
- The outcomes of the sustainability assessment define also under which conditions the PUReSmart circular innovative solution is also “sustainable”
- Sustainability performances are affected by the context, meant as the geographic, cultural, environmental setting in which relations take place. The outcomes of the assessment can support actors and stakeholders along the PU value chain in making decisions for ensuring that the implementation of the technology will enhance the positive environmental, economic and social aspects.

Analysed systems

The analysis considered the double functions played by the PUReSmart technology: the management of EoL mattresses and the production of recycled polyols and isocyanates.

The environmental assessment was carried out as a comparative assessment, i.e., PUReSmart technology was compared with the current technologies for EoL management and polyols&isocyanates production. Two comparative assessments were set up:

- comparison of two EoL PU-based mattresses management system, i.e., with and without PUReSmart technologies, in 2030, when the PUReSmart technology will be operative into the market. Results could support future decision in terms of improving the environmental sustainability of innovative recycling solutions
- comparison of the environmental impact of polyols and isocyanates production via the PUReSmart

technology with the virgin ones, produced with the conventional industrial processes.

The social analysis took an absolute perspective, looking at the identification of the most relevant social aspects – both positive and negative – connected with the development and implementation of the PUReSmart technology. Only a few social aspects are inherent to the technology, while most of them are due to the behaviour of people and organisations.

PUReSmart system

PUReSmart technology

Social Analysis

Social analysis

Material social aspects, social risks and benefits of innovative PU chemical recycling

Focus on key methodological concepts

Social LCA is a methodology for assessing positive and negative social impacts, performances and risks of products along their life cycle, with the ultimate goal of improving human dignity and wellbeing.

Materiality assessment is the process of evaluating and identifying social topics that matters to organizations and stakeholders because of their actual or potential impacts (UNEP, 2022).

Social topics are social issues of concern, both positive and negative, according to which impacts, performances and risks are evaluated.

Social risk is a measure of the likelihood of negative effects only (damage, injury, loss) that may be avoided through preventive actions.

Stakeholders are groups of people who experience and are affected by the behaviour of organizations, and at the same time who can affect the product life cycle with their own behaviour.

Methodological settings

The **social effects of a technology depend on how the technology is used and how it interacts** with the technological, physical, and behavioural context in which it will be embedded.

Therefore, at an early-design phase, the **Social LCA is applied at a qualitative level** to identify social topics of concern and social risks which currently characterize those sectors

and geographical contexts where the PReSmart technology could be implemented and used.

Goal of the assessment

The purpose of the social analysis was to define the most relevant social topics (social themes where potential impacts - negative and positive - might occur) related to the introduction of innovative chemical recycling technologies for PU EoL mattresses, considering a scenario of high penetration into the EU market.

The analysis also aimed at providing a preliminary overview of the potential socio-economic risks and effects for different stakeholder groups.

Results: Material social topics and their relevance

“*which are the relevant socio-economic aspects related to the waste management system of PU EoL mattresses, when chemical recycling technologies and secondary raw materials exploitation will be strengthened?*”

The **social materiality assessment** was carried out to identify **what is important to monitor and measure to reduce or prevent social impacts**, when the technology will be implemented, and what are the potential benefits generated by such a technological system. **A topic is material if**

- a product and its life cycle is likely to have a high positive or negative impact on the stakeholders and the business
- the intended audience finds a topic very relevant and desires to have in-

formation on it

Starting out from the social topics included in the Methodological Sheets for Subcategories in Social Life Cycle Assessment (UNEP, 2021) and the Handbook for Product Social Impact Assessment (Goedkoop et al., 2020), stakeholders along the EU PU value chain were engaged in a workshop to discuss about social topics of concern for chemical recycling technologies and to provide feedbacks on their relevance.

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Material Social Topics
(ranked from the slightly important to the very important) and 6 stakeholder groups (users/consumers, local communities, society, value chain actors, small scale entrepreneurs)

11

Important social topics,
6 moderately important social topics,
2 slightly important social topics

	Small-scale entrepreneurs				
Important	Product quality Health and Safety End-of-Life responsibility Transparency	Safe and Healthy Living Conditions	Technology Development Public Commitment to Sustainability Issues	Fair competition Eco-industrial partnership Supplier relationships and fair trading	Supplier relationships and fair trading
moderately important	Feedback mechanism	Contribution to economic development	Respect of intellectual properties rights	Promoting social responsibility	
slightly important		Community engagement Access to immaterial and material resources	Corruption	Wealth distribution Women's empowerment	Women's empowerment

Results: Social risks

“*which are the potential social risks characterizing the sectors in which the PReSmart technology can be implemented?*”

The analysis of social risks is helpful to highlight what might be potential risks in those sectors in which the PReSmart technology could be implemented, namely: chemical, recycling and furniture sector.

The evaluation was carried out by means of the PSILCA database³.

HIGHLIGHTS:

For all the analysed sectors, the highest risks concern mainly the stakeholders local community and workers, and are related to the social topics access to material resources, fair salary and workers' rights

Additional social risks of concern are also represented by:

- contribution to economic development, in the chemical and furniture sectors
- migration, in the waste recycling and furniture sectors
- health and safety, in the waste recycling sector

3

Reference sectors
chemical products, waste recycling, furniture.

4

Reference countries
BE, FR, NL, DE.

Social topics are clustered into three levels of risks - **I level, II level and III level** - on the basis of the social risks characterizing the reference sector. The **level of risk represents the level of priority of intervention and/**

or attention, i.e., how urgent or how much attention a social topic needs to reduce or avoid social impacts when the PReSmart technology will be implemented.

	Workers			
I level	Access to material resources Contribution to economic development Migration Safe and healthy living conditions	Contribution to economic development	Corruption Promoting social responsibility	Fair salary Forced labour Health and safety_w Social benefits, legal issues Workers' rights
II level		Health and safety		Child labour Discrimination
III level	Environmental Footprints GHG footprint Local employment Respect of indigenous rights	Prevention and mitigation of conflicts	Fair competition	Working time

3 <https://psilca.net/>

Results: Social effects

“*which are the potential social effects driven by the introduction of PReSmart technology?*”

For each of the identified material social topics, socio-economic effects in the medium and long term were identified, by means of interviews to project partners, as stakeholders of the PU value chain.

The type of effect is expressed in terms of positive, negative or neutral outcome, together with a qualitative description of it.

HIGHLIGHTS:

Overall positive effects are foreseen in terms of access to immaterial and material resources, contribution to economic development, fair competition, product quality, promoting social responsibility, public commitment to sustainability issues and technology development.

Negative effects are not identified across social topics, but effects on the end-of-life responsibility and transparency would depend on how the communication on the new recycling systems will be delivered to waste owners and actors in the PU value chain.

As for the remaining social topics the effects of PReSmart technology are unknown or not expected by the technology per se (. community engagement, feedback mechanism).

When considering the management of EoL mattresses, socio-economic effects are expected mainly in terms of end-of-life responsibility and technology transfer, since the technology application could be expanded to other materials.

When considering polyols and isocyanates production, the main socio-economic effects are expected in term of access to immaterial and material resources – because materials recycling potentially avoid raw material extraction - and product quality thanks to the production of high-quality secondary raw materials. The introduction of PReSmart technology could effectively provide a new opportunity of promoting sustainability issues in the PU value chain, but transparency will be fundamental to guarantee traceability and safety on the recycled material, thus enhancing interest and trust on the final consumer.

Focus on key methodological concepts

The identification of social risks goes beyond the specific PReSmart technology but consider broadly what are the inherent risks of the analysed sectors: it represents then a warning for the future managers of the PReSmart technology
The evaluation of social effects has specifically considered the PReSmart technology and the EU reference market for its implementation.

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“Technology is neither good nor bad; nor is it neutral.”

Its social effects depend on how the technology is used and how organizations behave

(Kranzberger 1997).

Potential socio-economic effects driven by the introduction of the technology

Positive effects	Neutral effects	Points of attention
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Access to immaterial and material resources - Contribution to economic development - Fair competition - Product quality - Promoting social responsibility - Public commitment to sustainability issues - Technology development 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Community engagement - Feedback mechanisms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - End-of-life responsibility - Transparency <p>(depending on the communication on the new recycling systems to waste owners and actors in the PU value chain)</p>

Highest social risks characterising the sectors and country where the technology will be introduced

- Access to material resources
- Fair salary
- Contribution to economic development
- Workers' rights
- Migration
- Health and safety for workers and local communities

A more detailed description of the social topics is available by scanning this Qr Code

Environmental Assessment

Environmental assessment

Potential environmental impacts and benefits of the PReSmart chemical recycling technology, quantified with the Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) methodology

Objectives and set up

The goal of the environmental assessment is to measure the capability of PReSmart recycling technology of reducing the environmental impact of EoL management of PU-based mattresses, turning a PU waste stream into its chemical constituents that can replace virgin polyols and isocyanates.

The Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodology has been applied, building upon the PEF approach for addressing end of life processes⁴. A broad set of environmental impact categories was considered, to avoid

Scenarios comparison:

- **Baseline vs PReSmart for EoL management of PU-based mattresses**

GOALS OF THE STUDY

To quantify the potential environmental impact of PU-based mattresses EoL management system, with and without PReSmart solution.

Two technology systems of the EoL management of PU-based mattresses were compared:

- **current EoL management system**, in which conventional chemical recycling is applied together with other EoL technologies. The PReSmart technology is not part of the scenario
- **innovative system, with the PReSmart solution**, characterised by a smart chemical recycling coupled with a smart sorting pre-treatment step, allowing the recovery of polyols and isocyanates with high purity, suitable to be used in the production of new PU-based products.

neglecting important consequences on e.g., different impact categories, geographic areas or stages of the life cycle

The PReSmart recycling technology fulfils two main functions, namely i) recycling of EoL PU-based mattresses and ii) production of secondary raw materials such as polyols and isocyanates. Two different scenarios were developed, to capture both functionalities and compare them with current available alternative on the market.

Scenario comparison:

- **Conventional vs PReSmart chemolysis**

GOALS OF THE STUDY

To quantify the environmental impact of the recycled polyols and isocyanates obtained with the PReSmart technology and compare them with virgin products.

To properly compare these two products, the environmental impact of the end-of-life management system of PU-based mattresses – a function fulfilled by the PReSmart technology – needs to be added to the **production of virgin polyols** to make the two systems functionally equivalent.

⁴ The Circular Footprint Formula was applied for dealing with material production and end of life along the product's value chain, according to COMMISSION RECOMMENDATION (EU) 2021/2279 of 15 December 2021 on the use of the Environmental Footprint methods to measure and communicate the life cycle environmental performance of products and organisations

Scenarios definition

Collection rate	Sorting rate (efficiency on collected)	Dismantling rate (efficiency on sorted)
15%	55%	93%

The **collection** was assumed to be performed with lorries collecting furniture and mattresses from the various disposal sites.

The collected mattresses are transported to a **sorting** plant, where the different flows are sorted based on the suitability of mattresses to be recycled.

In the **dismantling and preparation** phase, the PU-based mattresses are isolated and prepared to be sent

to the recycling facilities. During this phase, materials (such as textiles) are sent to different EoL management facilities, and the PU-based mattresses are sent to the recycling facility.

The last phase is **recycling** the material fractions in output from the dismantling. The current technologies employed to recycle PU-based material are chemical and mechanical recycling, and pyrolysis.

BASELINE SCENARIO

In the baseline scenario, the **current EoL management system** was analysed considering the normative evolution of EPR (Extended Producer Responsibility) schemes in Europe in 2030.

More in detail, the logistics of the system and the collection and recovery targets are based on the French EPR scheme.

PUReSmart SCENARIO

In the PUReSmart scenario, the assumptions for the collection, sorting, dismantling, and preparation steps were the same as for the baseline scenario. The same assumptions are also adopted for distances among facilities and transport means. The reference year is 2030.

Compared to the baseline scenario, a **Smart Sorting step** was introduced to separate the PU by main fami-

lies and thus ensure the chemolysis process's quality. After the sorting, the collected PU material is sent to the **Smart Chemolysis phase**, assumed to occur in the same facility. The smart chemolysis allows a high recovery of high-quality polyols and isocyanates, which can be used as raw materials for new PU-based products.

Results

Scenarios comparison: environmental impact of 1 ton of collected mattresses

The results of the environmental impact category Climate Change are reported, for the purpose of illustrating

the results. Climate Change is also one of the most relevant impact categories of the analysis.

Baseline	Environmental categories, characterisation, 1 ton of collected mattresses	PUReSmart
9.73E+02	Climate Change (total), [kg CO2 eq.]	4.17E+02

The results show that the PUReSmart solutions can reduce by 50% the potential environmental impact of the EoL manage-

ment of PU-based mattresses, compared to current technologies and systems.

Scenarios comparison: environmental hotspots of life cycle phases and processes

Baseline	Climate Change, fossil Phases and processes of the analysed scenario	PUReSmart
Sorting		
	Mechanical recycling (credit)	33.6%
<1%	Electricity consumption	<1%
8.1%	Electricity (credit)	6.0%
1.4%	PU waste (landfill)	1.7%
76.6%	PU waste (incineration)	48.8%
13.6%	Thermal energy (credit)	10.0%
<1%	Transports	
PU recycling		
3.7%	Mechanical recycling (credit)	
1.5%	Pyrolysis	
94.8%	Chemical recycling	

The processes described as 'credit' represent the environmental impact that could be avoided by recovering secondary raw materials or energy, that can replace the conventional production of virgin raw materials and primary energy. **The sorting step is the one that contributes most to the overall impact on Climate Change of both the management systems, baseline and PUReSmart.** This is mainly due to the incineration of waste, i.e., the share of PU mattresses that is not suitable to be recycled. In a future perspective of sustainable industrial development, **Smart Sorting could be further improved by reducing the share of PU waste that goes to incineration.**

Among the PU recycling technologies of the baseline scenario, i.e., conventional chemical recycling, mechanical recycling and pyrolysis, the **current chemical recycling technologies are the ones responsible of the highest share of potential impact of the current EoL management system.**

The comparison between the final products, i.e., polyols&isocyanates, highlights the promising results of recovered PUReSmart products, with potential impact reduction on all the relevant impact categories but water consumption, the latter due to the processes involved in the Smart Chemolysis.

HIGHLIGHTS:

Results pointed out that replacing current chemical recycling with the PReSmart recycling system could remarkably reduce the environmental impact of EoL management of PU-based mattresses.

The replacement of current chemical recycling with the Smart Sorting and Smart Chemolysis system reduced the overall impact of the PU-based waste management system by 50%, thanks to the recovery of large quantities of high-purity secondary raw materials.

The environmental performances of the PReSmart solution can be further improved thanks to energy efficiency measures that can be implemented in the industrialisation step.

Considering that the PReSmart technologies have currently be developed at TRL5, the scale-up at industrialisation scale could further improve the overall environmental performance.

Results confirmed the competitiveness – from the environmental point of view - of the PReSmart recovered polyols compared with the virgin ones, despite the different level of technology maturity.

Also in this case, the production scale plays a pivotal role in comparing the environmental impact of polyols. Further industrial improvements, especially in the consumption of energy and materials, will improve the overall environmental performance of PReSmart polyols&isocyanates.

PROS	CONS
<p>LOWER ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT OF PReSmart SOLUTION</p> <p>FURTHER ENVIRONMENTAL IMPROVEMENTS WITH INDUSTRIAL SCALE-UP</p>	<p>COMPARISON OF TECHNOLOGIES WITH DIFFERENT LEVEL OF MATURITY</p>

Competing with the extremely mature and efficient value chain of fossil fuel based raw materials is a potential bottleneck to bring new recycling technologies like PReSmart to the market. Incentives potentially will be

needed to bring this new PReSmart technology to economic viability, e.g., by addressing existing or new eco-fee(s) to this new value chain. Also, an EU legal obligation, to include a certain minimum amount of recycled

content recovered from post-consumer plastic waste would give a boost to the demand for recycled raw materials.

Conclusions

Chance to Change

The potential environmental impacts of the PURESmart technological system were quantified with the PEF methodology, complemented by the evaluation of relevant social topics and the identification of social risks.

Results pointed out the **potential of PURESmart solution in reducing environmental burdens** when managing EoL PU-based mattresses and when producing secondary polyols&isocyanates. There is also **potential for positive social impacts** in particular on workers and local community, that can be achieved through the implementation of adequate management practices by the organisations that will operate the technology.

Potential environmental and social benefits from innovative PU Chemical Recycling Technology

Potential environmental and social benefits could be reached through the implementation of the innovative PURESmart technology. Pivotal will be the behaviour of all the actors of the PU value chain, for turning potential social risks into opportunities and for further improving and exploiting the already achieved environmental benefits, compared to current technologies for EoL management and polyols production.

The social analysis, based on the Social LCA methodology, was carried out to identify relevant social aspects for PURESmart and chemical recycling in general, and also risks which currently characterize sectors where the technology will be implemented (mainly waste management and chemical). The identification of relevant social topics involved different stakeholder groups, covering the PU value chain. Overall, nineteen relevant social aspects were identified as relevant, representing six stakeholder groups (users, local communities, society, value chain actors and small-scale entrepreneurs). The relevant social topics are those towards which efforts will be needed to avoid, reduce, or magnify the social effects due to the introduction of the innovative PURESmart recycling technology. Overall, **positive social effects are expected for the implementation of the PURESmart technology**, mainly in relation to access to immaterial and material resources, contribution to economic development, fair competition, product quality, promoting social responsibility,

public commitment to sustainability issues and technology development. **When considering the management of EoL mattresses, socio-economic effects are expected mainly in terms of end-of-life responsibility and technology transfer**, since the technology application could be expanded to other types of materials. **When considering polyols and isocyanates production, the main socio-economic effects are expected in term of access to immaterial and material resources**, since materials recycling avoids raw material extraction, and product quality thanks to the creation of high-quality secondary raw material. The introduction of PURESmart recycling technology could effectively provide a new opportunity of promoting sustainability issues in the PU value chain: transparency and communication will be key to guarantee traceability and safety on the recycled material, thus enhancing interest and trust of the final consumer.

The environmental assessment was carried out to quantify the environmental performance of the PURESmart recycling technology. The results highlight the role of PURESmart in significantly reducing the potential environmental impact of EoL management of PU-based mattresses and its competitiveness – from the environmental point of view – in producing secondary polyols&isocyanates out of the PU waste stream.

Recycling and recovering high-quality secondary raw materials are essential to ensure the sustainability and circularity of the PU-waste management system.

They are part of the solutions, together with the following elements:

- efforts in improving the collection, sorting, and dismantling rates;
- Increase of knowledge sharing among actors to support technology implementation within the existing waste management systems in the European countries, and circular design, both chemically and on product-level to ensure product quality (Van Gaubergen and Block, 2022);
- strong and continuous communication strategies to properly inform consumers on the PU waste management system (Van Gaubergen and Block, 2022);

- policy frameworks that promote circular systems, by increasing producer responsibility, facilitating waste collection and distribution (Van Gaubergen and Block, 2022);
- guarantee transparency on the product information to earn consumers' trust and interest on the new products (Van Gaubergen and Block, 2022);
- strengthen awareness about chemical recycling systems, to increase interest among the PU value chain actors and reach new market segments (Van Gaubergen and Block, 2022).

Partners

The PReSmart consortium involves nine partners from six different countries, covering the entire polyurethane reprocessing value chain.

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Project Coordinator
• **Bart Haelterman** / RECTICEL
haelterman.bart@recticel.com

Project Management Offucer
• **Maud Bossard** / BENKEI
maud@benkei.fr

References

European Commission (EC) 2019. COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE EUROPEAN COUNCIL, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS The European Green Deal COM/2019/640 final

European Commission (EC) 2020. COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS A new Circular Economy Action Plan For a cleaner and more competitive Europe COM/2020/98 final

European Commission (EC) 2022. Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL establishing a framework for setting ecodesign requirements for sustainable products and repealing Directive 2009/125/EC. Brussels, 30.3.2022 COM(2022) 142 final 2022/0095 (COD)

Europur, 2021a. The Netherlands: a world-leader in mattress recycling [Press release]. <https://europur.org/the-netherlands-a-world-leader-in-mattress-recycling/>

Europur, 2021b. The End-of-Life of flexible polyurethane foam from mattresses and furniture. An overview of regulatory drivers, recycling technologies and remaining challenges. EoL-Brochure-2021-EUROPUR.pdf

Goedkoop, M.J.; de Beer, I.M; Harmens, R.; Peter Saling; Dave Morris; Alexandra Florea; Anne Laure Hettinger; Diana Indrane; Diana Visser; Ana Morao; Elizabeth Musoke-Flores; Carmen Alvarado; Ipshita Rawat; Urs Schenker; Megann Head; Massimo Collotta; Thomas Andro; Jean-François Viot; Alain Whatelet; Product Social Impact Assessment Handbook - 2020, Amersfoort, November 1st, 2020.

UNEP, 2020. Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessment of Products and Organizations 2020. Benoît Norris, C., Traverso, M., Neugebauer, S., Ekener, E., Schaubroeck, T., Russo Garrido, S., Berger, M., Valdivia, S., Lehmann, A., Finkbeiner, M., Arcese, G. (eds.). United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP).

UNEP, 2021. Methodological Sheets for Subcategories in Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) 2021. Traverso, M., Valdivia, S., Luthin, A., Roche, L., Arcese, G., Neugebauer, S., Petti, L., D'Eusanio, M., Tragnone, B.M., Mankaa, R., Hanafi, J., Benoît Norris, C., Zamagni, A. (eds.). United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP)

Van Gaubergen J. and Block T. PReSmart Project, Deliverable D5.4 Opportunities and barriers for scale-up: a TIS-perspective on innovation for chemical recycling of flexible PU foam. 2022. Confidential.

